

Quantum Wavelength and Frequency Linked to the Classical Action?

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In previous notes (1) we discussed how $(p=0, E=m_0c^2)$ $(x=0, t_0)$ transforms to p', E', x', t' such that $x'/t'=v$. We noted that $(x=0, t_0)$ is a special (x,t) vector linked to a stationary frame. We noted that a general vector $(x,t) = (0,t) + (x,0)$ and that $(x,0)$ Lorentz transforms such that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px=0$. We also noted that E scales t and p scales x and argued that this was the basis for the frequency and wavelength for a quantum free particle.

In this note we investigate this idea further. In particular we argue that given $-Et+px$, it is not only the case that $(x,0)$ transforms into (x_1,t_1) such that $-E'x_1+p't_1=0$, but that $1/E=t$ and $1/p=x$ also yields $-E \cdot 1/E + p \cdot 1/p=0$. In other words there is freedom in both t and x proportional to $1/E$ and $1/p$ even though the special vector $(0,t_0)$ defines the velocity i.e. $x'/t'=v$. This freedom may be associated with uncertainty in position and time even though there is a well defined $x'/t'=v$. This uncertainty has important consequences if interactions occur i.e. interference effects. These are usually associated with a wave which has the dispersion relationship $E=pv$, but we argue that they also hold for a particle with rest mass i.e. $p=E(v)/v$ because it is the uncertainty in t and x which keeps $-Et+px=0$ which is the source. This also happens to hold for a photon which is a wave in the sense that it has no rest mass. The uncertainty itself yields the velocity i.e. $x/t = 1/p / (1/E) = E/p = c$.

Given the periodic nature of $-E \cdot 1/E + p \cdot 1/p=0$ i.e. $-E \cdot n/E + p \cdot n/p = 0$ where $n=1,2,3\dots$ we argue that a periodic function be sought such that it describes a kind of probability due to uncertainty in x,t , but this uncertainty disappears when $t=n/E$ and $x=n/p$.

Classical Action for a Particle with Rest Mass

In (1) we argued that one may consider a rest frame in which there is localized energy, but no overall momentum and hence no overall velocity. It is possible to consider a particle at rest with "rest mass" or two particles with rest mass, one moving to the right the other to the left such that their momenta cancel and such that there are mutual interactions so that each bounce back and forth. The same idea may be applied to an object (e.g. box) with rest mass and a photon. The main idea seems to be that energy is localized. This suggests a special (x,t) vector namely $(x=0, t_0)$. Given a Lorentz transformation, however, and the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, one may choose any x,t . If one chooses $(x=0, t_0)$ it transforms to $x'/t'=v$. A more general $(x,t) = (0,t) + (x,0)$. In the rest frame $-0 \cdot m_0 + 0 \cdot x = 0$ and if one transforms $(x,0)$ its dot product with (p,E) is also zero. Thus from the point of view of $-Et+px$ one may use the special coordinate $(x=0, t_0)$ which transforms such that $x'/t' = v$ thus defining velocity.

$x=1/p, t=1/E$ in $-Et+px$

For a particle with rest mass, the special rest frame is linked to the special vector $(x=0, t_0)$ as argued above. In any frame, however, one may add $x_1=b_1/p$ and $t_1=b_1/E$ such that $-Et+px=0$. Thus there is the special $(x=0, t_0)$ which yields x'/t' defining velocity, but also an uncertainty in position and time (not defining velocity) namely $x_1=1/p$ and $t_1=1/E$ which leaves $-Et+px$

unchanged. This we argue is the reason for the wavelength and frequency in a quantum free particle. It is also linked to the scaling of t by E and x by p in $-Et+px$. The Lorentz transformation for $A = -Et+px$ may have a set of solutions which yield the same value of A . In particular, there is (x',t') such that $x'/t'=v$, but also $x'+n/p$ and $t'+n/E$ where $n=1,2,3,\dots$. This we argue seems to suggest a periodicity in the problem. For example, one does not wish to choose a large n and have large uncertainty, rather cycling seems to be a better solution

In such a case, one may consider a periodic function representing probability such that at $x=bn/p$ and $t=bn/E$ where b is a constant one has the classical constant velocity result. In between these points one may have unusual behaviour i.e wave like uncertainty described by $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ which have a modulus of 1 i.e. conserve probability. This requires two dimensions. Furthermore, x linked to bn/p and t linked to bn/E are independent. The velocity is already tracked by $x'/t'=v$ from $(x=0, t_0)$ in the stationary frame. In such a case $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$ is a solution.

(p,E) linked to (x,t)

It is interesting to note that this approach follows only if one uses the invariant $-Et+px$ i.e. links (p,E) and (x,t) . This is not necessarily unusual because the special rest frame is defined as one in which p total is 0 and energy is localized i.e. one may place an origin in this region. Thus two conditions are needed, one linked to momentum $p=0$ and the other to x i.e. $x=0$. This leads to the two vectors $(0, t_0)$ and $(x=0, t_0)$. Thus considering (p,E) and (x,t) together in an invariant expression $A = -Et+px$ is not unusual. It keeps the two conditions together which, however, leads to shifts in t and x (i.e. uncertainty) which maintains A constant. Thus there is not simply $(x=0, t_0)$ which yields $x'/t'=v$, but also an uncertainty of $x=1/p$ and $t=1/E$ which we link to periodic changes in $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$. These uncertainty values do not define velocity, rather the particle (with rest mass) moves with its velocity which defines p and E , but these in turn define uncertainty regions in x and t . The uncertainty regions in x are particularly important because many interactions are spatial and so this leads to probability being involved in interactions such as one with two slits etc i.e. interference type interactions. It is not enough that one $x'/t'=v$, there is also the uncertainty of the wavelength proportional to $1/p$.

Photon

In the case of a photon, there is no stationary frame i.e. one in which the photon momentum is 0 so there is also no special vector $(x=0, t_0)$. Nevertheless the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ still holds. Thus there should be uncertainty linked to t proportional to $1/E$ and x proportional to $1/p$. These give $A=0$. $A=0$, however, is also linked with $E/p = x/t$ which is wave velocity, namely that of light. Thus both the uncertainty and the velocity are connected because they both yield $A=0$. They are one and the same. For the particle with rest mass the uncertainty x going as $1/p$ and t as $1/E$ yielded $A=0$, but A itself had a different value for $x'/t'=v$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although we have discussed in previous notes (1) the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ implying that E scaling t and p scaling x and have argued for special times and lengths proportional to $1/E$ and $1/p$, here we try to show more formally how this uncertainty (in x and t) arises. An object with a rest mass has a special stationary frame characterized by total $p=0$ (there could be moving components, but the overall p must add to zero) and a center of localization e.g. $x=0$ at $t=t_0$. Thus (p,E) and (x,t) are linked we argue. As a consequence we argue that they should be considered together which is what the Lorentz invariant $A=-Et+px$ accomplishes. $(x=0, t_0)$ transforms to x',t' such that $x'/t'=v$. For a general (x,t) instead of $(x=0,t_0)$ $(x,t)=(x=0,t_0) + (x,0)$ with $(x,0)$ transforming such that $-E't' + p'x'=0$. There is another solution, however, which allows for uncertainty in x and t and leaves A unchanged namely t proportional to b/E and x proportional to b/p where b is a constant. Thus there may be a particle with rest mass moving at $x'/t'=v=\text{constant}$, yet its position and time may have uncertainty when considered with respect to $A=-Et+px$. We suggest a periodic function may deal with this uncertainty instead of b/E and b/p where b could be large. Thus we suggest a probability of the form $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$. T and x are not linked in the sense of velocity, but rather independently measure cycling uncertainty in time and position. For interactions which are often of a spatial nature such as a two slit apparatus $\exp(ipx)$ becomes the important probability factor.

In the case of a photon there is no stationary frame and so no special $(x=0, t_0)$. $A=0=-Et+px$ yields the photon velocity i.e. $E=pc$. The uncertainty in x and t , however, still exist, but also yield $A=0$ i.e. $-E(1/E) + p(1/p)=0$ so there is velocity of c , $E=pc$ as the dispersion relationship, but $1/E$ and $1/p$ describe uncertainties in t and x linked to wave motion.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relationship Between Zero and NonZero Rest Mass in Special Relativity (preprint, zenodo, 2022)